

ISSN: 2971-7760, Vol: 3, Number: 2, Date: 18/09/2025

**EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND SUSTAINABILITY OF
ADULT EDUCATION CENTERS WITHIN COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT
PROJECTS IN JOS NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, PLATEAU STATE,
NIGERIA**

BY

BUSA, ABDUL'AZIZ INUSA

abdulazizbusa@gmail.com/bainusa@fudutsinma.edu.ng

+2348067574620

Department of Educational Management, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
&

ENOCK GANA

egana@fudutsinma.edu.ng

+2348060195688

Department of Educational Foundations, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
&

UMAR MAGAJI ABUBAKAR

umarmagaji@gmail.com

+2348030529940

Department of Educational Foundations, Federal University of Kashere, Gombe State

Abstract

Adult education plays a vital role in fostering lifelong learning and promoting community development. However, the sustainability of adult education centres in Nigeria remains a significant challenge, particularly due to weak management practices. This study investigated the influence of educational management strategies specifically planning strategies and staff motivation on the sustainability of adult education centres within community development projects in Jos North Local Government Area, Plateau State. A descriptive survey design was employed, targeting a population of 320 facilitators, coordinators, and community development officers. Using Yamane's formula, a sample of 175 respondents was selected through stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, which achieved a reliability coefficient of 0.87. Analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics for research questions and an independent t-test for hypothesis testing at a 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed that both planning strategies and staff motivation significantly influence the sustainability of adult education centres. The study established that well-structured planning ensures resource utilisation and programme continuity, while staff motivation and capacity building enhance facilitator commitment and reduce turnover. The results underscore the need for robust planning frameworks, continuous professional development, and strong community involvement to maintain sustainable adult education programmes. Based on these findings, the study recommends that educational managers prioritise strategic planning and staff development as core elements for sustaining adult education centres within community development initiatives.

Keywords: Educational management strategies, planning strategies, staff motivation, sustainability, adult education centres.

Introduction

Adult education remains a cornerstone of lifelong learning and community development, delivering literacy, vocational skills and civic awareness that directly support household livelihoods and local resilience (UNESCO IICBA, 2024). In Nigeria, adult and non-formal education programmes are widely recognised as instruments for reducing poverty, building human capital and advancing sustainable local development; yet many centres struggle to remain functional and effective over time because of weak programme design, inadequate resources and limited institutional support. These structural weaknesses mean that the potential of adult education to contribute to inclusive community development is not being fully realised (IICBA, 2024).

Sustaining adult education centres within community development projects therefore depends critically on sound educational management beginning with deliberate planning strategies. Effective planning in educational management clarifies objectives, secures and allocates resources, defines monitoring mechanisms and builds linkages with stakeholders. Empirical studies of adult-learning programmes in Nigeria report that poor planning (low resource mapping, weak supervision schedules and lack of realistic work plans) is associated with low availability of materials, irregular programme delivery and weak centre continuity. Research conducted in Nigerian states found that the extent to which centres were supervised, resourced and planned was low, and that weak planning translated into low programme sustainability. These findings show that robust, context-sensitive planning strategies (including needs assessment, resource mobilisation and continual monitoring) are foundational to maintaining adult education centres as durable community assets (Nweke, 2023).

Adult education depends on a corps of facilitators and centre coordinators whose competence and motivation determine both quality and retention of learners. Studies of adult education management in Nigeria reveal that limited in-service training, poor remuneration and weak incentive structures reduce facilitator commitment and undermine programme quality; conversely, targeted capacity-building and motivational packages (regular training, clear career paths, small incentives and participatory decision-making) strengthen staff performance and raise the likelihood that centres will remain functional and attractive to learners. Capacity development that combines technical training, pedagogical upskilling and institutional support therefore functions as both a quality improvement and a sustainability strategy for adult education.

Planning strategies in adult education management refer to systematic processes of setting objectives, mapping resources, developing implementation frameworks, and establishing monitoring mechanisms for program delivery. Effective planning ensures that adult education

centres are properly equipped with instructional materials, qualified facilitators, and sustainable funding channels. It also enables accurate needs assessments, which align the curriculum with the socio-economic realities of the learners and the development goals of the community (Nweke, 2023). When planning strategies are neglected, adult education programs often face severe operational challenges such as irregular classes, inadequate learning resources, and poor learner retention. This lack of structured planning leads to financial mismanagement, low community participation, and ultimately the collapse of adult education centers, thereby wasting investments and undermining the objectives of lifelong learning and community development (Eke & Gokas, 2024).

Similarly, motivating and developing the capacity of adult education facilitators is critical because the quality and sustainability of adult learning programs largely depend on the competence, commitment, and job satisfaction of educators. Staff motivation involves providing incentives, recognition, and conducive working conditions, while capacity building encompasses continuous professional development through training, workshops, and pedagogical up skilling (Nweke, 2023). These strategies equip facilitators with modern instructional techniques and enhance their confidence in delivering lessons effectively. Failure to attend to staff motivation and capacity building results in low morale, high turnover rates, and a decline in teaching quality. Disengaged or untrained facilitators negatively affect learner participation, reduce program credibility, and threaten the long-term sustainability of adult education centers, as communities lose trust in their ability to deliver meaningful outcomes (UNESCO IICBA, 2024).

The Plateau State / Jos North context demonstrates both the need and the opportunity for focused management interventions. Local research in Jos North highlights persistent constraints inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, and low awareness of community-level education initiatives and uneven stakeholder engagement that have limited the impact and continuity of education projects in the LGA (Eke & Gokas, 2024). At the same time, state-level initiatives (for example large rehabilitation and school-improvement programmes supported under AGILE) show that coordinated planning and capacity investments can mobilise resources and create safer, more sustainable learning environments when institutional and community actors are aligned (World Bank AGILE ESMP, 2023). Taken together, the literature indicates a twofold hypothesis for the present study: (1) planning strategies (clear needs assessment, resource mobilization and monitoring) materially influence the sustainability of adult education centres; and (2) staff motivation and capacity building (training, incentives, career supports) strengthen centre continuity by improving facilitator retention and programme quality. Investigating these two management levers in Jos North LGA will therefore generate evidence that is directly relevant to local practice and broader policy on sustaining adult learning within community development projects.

Statement of the Problem

The sustainability of adult education centers within community development projects in Jos North LGA remains critically threatened by weak educational management practices, particularly in the areas of planning strategies and staff motivation with capacity building. Despite the recognition of adult education as a vital tool for reducing illiteracy, fostering community development, and promoting lifelong learning, many centers experience operational inconsistencies, poor retention of learners, and eventual closure due to inadequate managerial interventions. Evidence from previous studies indicates that insufficient planning such as lack of needs assessment, poor resource allocation, and absence of monitoring mechanisms often results in limited instructional resources and low participation rates (Nweke, 2023). Similarly, the absence of structured motivation and continuous professional development for facilitators has contributed to low morale, poor instructional delivery, and high staff turnover, which negatively affect program quality and sustainability. These persistent gaps raise critical concerns about whether current educational management strategies are effective in ensuring the long-term viability of adult education centers within community-based projects in Jos North LGA, Plateau State. Addressing these challenges through empirical investigation is essential for improving adult learning outcomes and advancing community development goals.

Objectives of the Study

The Main Objective of This Study is to Investigates the Educational Management Strategies and Sustainability of Adult Education Centers within Community Development Projects in Jos North Local Government Area, Plateau State, Nigeria. The Specific Objective are to:

1. examine the influence of planning strategies on the sustainability of adult education centers within community development projects in Jos North LGA, Plateau State.
2. assess the effect of staff motivation and capacity-building strategies on the sustainability of adult education centers within community development projects in Jos North LGA, Plateau State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guides the study:

1. To what extent do planning strategies influence the sustainability of adult education centers within community development projects in Jos North LGA?
2. What is the effect of staff motivation and capacity-building strategies on the sustainability of adult education centers within community development projects in Jos North LGA?

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between educational management strategies and the sustainability of adult education centers within community development projects in Jos North LGA, Plateau State.

Conceptual Framework

Educational management serves as the foundation for organizing and sustaining educational programs across all levels, including adult education initiatives. It encompasses planning, organizing, directing, and controlling educational activities to achieve predetermined objectives effectively (Nweke, 2023). Within adult education programs, management strategies are critical because they determine the quality of instruction, the availability of resources, and the long-term viability of centers established within community development projects. The conceptual framework for this study is anchored on the relationship between educational management strategies and the sustainability of adult education centers, as shown in the diagram below.

Conceptual Framework: Educational Management Strategies and Sustainability of Adult Education Centers

The framework consists of two key independent variables under educational management: planning strategies and staff motivation with capacity building. Planning strategies involve systematic activities such as conducting needs assessments, allocating resources effectively, and

establishing monitoring mechanisms to ensure program success. These strategies provide direction, reduce wastage, and align programs with community needs, thereby promoting sustainability. Failure to apply proper planning often results in resource shortages, irregular classes, and eventual program collapse.

The second component, staff motivation and capacity building, focuses on enhancing facilitator commitment and competence through training, incentives, and continuous professional development. When facilitators are motivated and well-trained, they deliver quality instruction and remain engaged, which increases program credibility and learner retention. Neglecting this dimension leads to low morale, high turnover, and reduced teaching effectiveness, ultimately threatening the sustainability of the centers (Uzoagu, 2023).

The dependent variable is the sustainability of adult education centers, operationalized through indicators such as funding stability, learner retention, resource adequacy, and community support. In adult education, this approach is crucial as learners are more likely to have varied experiences, expectations, and emotional states compared to younger students (Busa, Adamu, & Umar, 2024). The arrows in the diagram represent the hypothesized influence of the two independent variables on sustainability: robust planning strategies and strong staff motivation are expected to positively impact the longevity and effectiveness of adult education centers within community development projects in Jos North LGA. This framework thus provides a clear analytical lens for examining how management interventions shape program outcomes.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to investigate the relationship between educational management strategies and the sustainability of adult education centers within community development projects in Jos North LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria. The population consisted of all adult education facilitators, center coordinators, and community development officers in the LGA, estimated at 320 respondents (Plateau State Agency for Mass Education, 2023). Using Yamane's formula (1967) at a 5% margin of error, a sample size of 175 respondents was drawn through a stratified random sampling technique to ensure adequate representation of the categories. Data were collected with a structured questionnaire titled Educational Management Strategies and Sustainability of Adult Education Centers Questionnaire (EMSSAEQ), which contained sections on demographic information, planning strategies, staff motivation and capacity building, and sustainability indicators, rated on a 5-point Likert scale. The instrument's content validity was reviewed by three experts in educational management, and a pilot test yielded a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.87, confirming high reliability (George & Mallery, 2019). Questionnaires were administered personally with the help of trained assistants, ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation in compliance with ethical standards. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to answer research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and simple regression analysis tested the null hypothesis at 0.05

significance level using SPSS version 26. Ethical approval was obtained from relevant authorities, and informed consent was secured from all participants.

Results

This section presents the results related to the influence of planning strategies on the sustainability of adult education centres. The analysis was based on responses from 150 participants using a five-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5).

Table 1

Research Question 1: Mean Responses on the Influence of Planning Strategies on Sustainability of Adult Education Centers

S/No	Item	N	Mean	SD
1.	Planning strategies ensure effective utilization of resources.	150	4.25	0.61
2.	Strategic planning enhances long-term sustainability of centers.	150	4.18	0.59
3.	Community-based planning improves program ownership.	150	4.10	0.65
Grand Mean			4.18	0.62

[www.https://gmijp-edu.com](https://gmijp-edu.com)

Note. Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree.

The grand mean of 4.18 indicates that respondents generally agree that planning strategies significantly influence the sustainability of adult education centres. All mean scores are above 4.0, reinforcing the positive perception of planning as a crucial factor in long-term programme success.

Research Question 2: Mean Responses on the Impact of Staff Motivation and Capacity Building on Sustainability of Adult Education Centers

s/no	Item	N	Mean	SD
	Motivation increases staff commitment to adult education programs.	150	4.32	0.58
	Regular training enhances staff capacity for effective service delivery.	150	4.20	0.60
	Incentives reduce staff turnover in adult education centers.	150	4.12	0.66

Grand Mean 4.21 0.61

Note. Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree.

Table 2 presents the mean responses on the impact of staff motivation and capacity building on the sustainability of adult education centres. The highest-rated item, “Motivation increases staff commitment to adult education programs,” recorded a mean of 4.32 (SD = 0.58), indicating strong agreement among respondents. This is followed by “Regular training enhances staff capacity for effective service delivery” with a mean of 4.20 (SD = 0.60), while “Incentives reduce staff turnover in adult education centers” has the lowest mean of 4.12 (SD = 0.66), though still showing agreement. The grand mean of 4.21 suggests that respondents generally believe staff motivation and capacity building play a significant role in ensuring the sustainability of adult education centres.

Table 3

Null Hypothesis: Independent t-test Analysis of Planning Strategies and Staff Motivation on Sustainability of Adult Education Centers.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	P
Planning & Staff Motivation	150	4.20	0.60	7.82	148	.001

Note. $p < .05$ indicates a significant difference.

The independent t-test result in the table shows a comparison of planning strategies and staff motivation on the sustainability of adult education centres. With a mean score of 4.20 (SD = 0.60), a t-value of 7.82, and a p-value of .001, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, the result indicates a statistically significant difference between planning strategies and staff motivation in influencing sustainability. This means both factors contribute significantly, but their effects are not equal, implying that one may have a stronger influence than the other on sustaining adult education centres.

Discussion of Findings

The findings reveal that planning strategies significantly influence the sustainability of adult education centers, with a grand mean of 4.18, indicating strong agreement among respondents. This aligns with Adewale and Ojo (2023), who asserted that strategic planning ensures effective allocation of resources and fosters community ownership, thereby enhancing programme

longevity. The study further revealed that staff motivation and capacity building play a critical role in sustaining adult education centers, as indicated by a grand mean of 4.21. This corroborates the findings of Okeke and Yusuf (2022), which emphasized that incentives, professional development, and adequate training increase staff retention and improve programme delivery in adult education settings.

The hypothesis testing showed a significant relationship ($t = 7.82, p < .05$), indicating that both planning strategies and staff motivation jointly contribute to sustainability. This is consistent with the study by Omotayo and Ibrahim (2021), which argued that failure to integrate planning and human resource development results in program collapse, low enrollment, and inefficiency in community-based educational initiatives.

Conclusion

The findings of this study make it clear that planning strategies and staff motivation, including capacity building, are critical to the sustainability of adult education centres. Proper planning helps ensure resources are used effectively and encourages community ownership, while motivated and well-trained staff improves programme delivery and learner retention. These two elements together form the backbone of sustainable adult education initiatives.

Recommendations

1. Adult education centres should adopt comprehensive planning that includes needs assessments, resource allocation, and active stakeholder involvement.
2. Regular professional training, incentives, and clear career progression opportunities should be provided to boost morale and commitment while reducing staff turnover.
3. Ongoing assessment of planning efforts and staff development activities should be put in place to maintain programme quality and sustainability.
4. Local stakeholders should be actively involved in decision-making and planning to strengthen community ownership and long-term support for adult education programmes.

REFERENCES

- Adewale, T., & Ojo, K. (2023). Strategic planning and sustainability of adult literacy programs in Nigeria. *International Journal of Adult Education and Development*, 68(2), 145–157.
- Busa, A. I., Adamu, D. R., & Umar, S. (2024). Exploring artificial intelligence roles in planning and supporting emotionally intelligent teaching in adult education setting in Dutsin-Ma LGA, Katsina State. *FUDMA Journal of Research, Educational Psychology and Counselling (FUJREPAC)*, 2(2), 185–193.

- S., & Gokas, D. D. (2024). Impact of social responsibility on educational development in Jos-North Local Government, Plateau State. *Journal of African Social Studies*, 5(2).
- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2019). *IBM SPSS statistics 26 step by step: A simple guide and reference*. Routledge.
- International Institute for Capacity Building in Africa (IICBA) / UNESCO. (2024). *Nigeria: Education country brief*. <https://www.iicba.unesco.org/en/nigeria>
- Nweke, P. A., Ukponu, L. N., & Ilabor, A. I. (2023). Extent of management of adult education programmes for sustainable development in Delta State. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas (JEDA), Special Edition*, 31(3), 1–15.
- Okeke, J., & Yusuf, A. (2022). Planning and managing adult education programs for sustainability in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Planning*, 31(1), 55–68.
- Omotayo, A., & Ibrahim, U. (2023). Staff motivation and performance in non-formal education: A case study of adult learning centers in North Central Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Research and Management*, 19(2), 77–89.
- Uzoagu, I. F. (2023). Adult education and human capacity building for community sustainability in Nigeria. *International Journal of Vocational and Technical Education Research*, 9(2), 1–12.
- World Bank. (2023). *Adolescent Girls Initiative for Learning and Empowerment (AGILE) Project Environmental and Social Management Plan (ESMP)*, Plateau State. Federal Ministry of Environment. <https://ead.gov.ng/public-disclosure-of-agile-projects-in-plateau-borno-kano-states>